

CONTEMPORARY FORMS OF RACISM AND BIGOTRY ON SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS

A new study reveals that Facebook has become a modern-day pillory for practising different sorts of racism, bigotry and related discriminations.

CONTEXT

The United Nations Human Rights Council in its latest report on contemporary forms of racism and related intolerance has classified racism on the internet and social media as a growing international concern. In Brazil, 58.3% of the population are active users of Facebook, spending an average of 3:43 hours per day on the social media platform. There has been a growing number of reported cases of racism on Facebook in Brazil (11,090 in 2014), raising concerns amongst civil society at large and, especially, within the Black community. Such racist discourses on Facebook can affect not only the person subject to the derogatory content but also his/her immediate family members, and the Black community as a whole.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Giving the fact that a considerable portion of Facebook users is composed of young people (in Brazil, 11.1 million users are aged 13-17 years), it is vital to implement educational initiatives in secondary schools. Pupils should be taught the following aspects:

- a. that the online and offline environment are not detached from each other, in such a way that the online attitudes do have real impacts on people's lives;
- b. the legal consequences of engaging in disseminating online racism;
- c. if they are exposed to this sort of inappropriate content, how to report them and to whom;
- d. how to avoid amplifying and reverberating the hateful voices, replicating the content across their own network.

The government should also foster educational campaigns raising awareness amongst the general public about the online environment and the fact it is not some sort of parallel dimension where civil society's norms and regulations do not apply. Such campaigns should be clear about the legal consequences of some of these actions.

Policymakers should push for the corporations behind the major social media platforms to implement more effective tools to remove hateful content flagged by their users. It has been noted that oftentimes their response time is very slow, allowing for the content to circulate in cyberspace for a long period of time.

The Privacy Policy of the corporations should make clear to its users that their social media platforms are not safe paradises for impunity, as some users believe they are. This means that, when requested by competent and genuine authorities, their personal data may be disclosed and they may be held responsible for their attitudes in accordance with the Brazilian rule of law.

KEY FINDINGS

1. 81% of the victims of racism on Facebook in Brazil are middle-class, well-educated, Black women aged between 20-35 years.
2. The Brazilian Facebook users who engage in disseminating bigotry are predominantly male (65.6% of the cases), in their early 20's and, oftentimes, they employ harsher vocabulary (mostly swear words) than female users to belittle Black women.
3. Eight thematic categories of events have been identified which trigger the publication of derogatory posts on Facebook towards Black women:
 - a. expressing disagreement with previous posts or negative comment made by someone else;
 - b. evidence of professional or academic engagement with 'noble' and prestigious careers (e.g.: medicine, journalism, law, engineering, etc.);
 - c. interracial relationship;
 - d. leading position in successful prime-time TV programmes either as a host or guest;
 - e. enjoying vacation abroad (especially towards Northern Hemisphere countries);
 - f. praising and/or using natural Afro hair style;
 - g. winning beauty contests;
 - h. rejection of dating proposition.
9. The *Endless Echo in Cyberspace Effect* – Derogatory Facebook posts can potentially engage new users for up to 3 years after the original publication (what is also called *Long Tail of Posts*). This amplifies the harm caused to people targeted by the posts and reinforces the bigotry for a long period of time.
10. Facebook users who engage in disseminating bigotry on the platform strongly believe that the online environment is a sort of “nobody’s land” and that online anonymity, or the adoption of an alias, can shield them from being found and held responsible for their attitudes.
11. Nevertheless, once a case of racism reaches the headlines in newspapers, the Facebook users who posted the derogatory content take one of the following initiatives:
 - a. shift their profile from public to private;
 - b. delete the derogatory post;
 - c. delete their account;
 - d. claim that it was just simply some sort of harmful innocent joke.
5. Facebook has become a modern-day pillory affording the proponents of colonial-like white supremacy ideologies the opportunity to perform virtual whipping (often concealed in derogatory humour). By engaging with like-minded people, they amplify the reach and reverberation of their voice in ways not previously seen in ordinary face-to-face social interactions in Brazil.
6. In the context of Facebook, the users who engage in dissemination of bigotry, racism and hate speech disregard any conventional social distances by targeting people that, in real life, they usually would not have access to. Research findings reveal that in 76.2% of the cases analysed, they have had no previous relationship with the victims.

THE AUTHOR

This policy brief was prepared by Luiz Valerio P. Trindade (PhD in Sociology | University of Southampton). It includes findings from his own PhD research entitled “It is not that funny. Critical analysis of racial ideologies embedded in racialized humour discourses on social media in Brazil”.
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